

EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONG EMPLOYEES WORKING IN IT INDUSTRY WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO BANGLADESH ABSTRACT

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Abstract:

Employee satisfaction and organisational performance have always been important issues for employees. Job performance at work is regarded by researchers as one of the most important domains in work and organizational psychology. Despite the fact that it is particularly studied in HRM and organizational behaviour and psychology, job performance is still not clearly defined nor conceptualized, and the empirical research done upon it does not always provide results that can be used. The main objective of the study is about the impact of organisational performance towards job satisfaction among employees in IT companies in Coimbatore. For this purpose, a sample of 150 was collected from the employees of the IT companies were percentage analysis, rank correlation and one way anova were used as tools to analyse the data. The conclusion is that the employees have a higher level of dissatisfaction towards the performance of the IT companies towards various factors which should take as a serious note to rectify the issues so that the level of satisfaction can be improved which leads to increase in productivity with employees in near future.

Key Words: Employee Performance, Job Satisfaction and IT industry

Introduction to the Study:

Job satisfaction or employee satisfaction has been defined in many ways. Some believe it is simply how content an individual is with his or her job, in other words, whether they like the job or individual aspects or facets of jobs, such as nature of work or supervision. Spector, P.E. (1997).

Job satisfaction is the most widely investigated job attitude, as well as one of the most extensively researched subjects in Industrial/Organizational Psychology. Many work motivation theories have represented the implied role of job satisfaction.

As a result of this expansive research, job satisfaction has been linked to productivity, motivation, absenteeism/tardiness, accidents, mental/physical health, and general life satisfaction. A common idea within the research has been that, to some extent, the emotional state of an individual is affected by interactions with their work environment. People identify themselves by their profession, such as a doctor, lawyer, or teacher. A person's individual well-being at work, therefore, is a very significant aspect of research.

The most widely accepted explanation of job satisfaction was presented by who defined job satisfaction as "a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job or job experiences". Additionally, job satisfaction has emotional, cognitive, and behavioral components. The emotional component refers to feelings regarding the job, such as boredom, anxiety, or excitement. The cognitive component of job satisfaction refers to beliefs regarding one's job, for example, feeling that one's job is mentally demanding and challenging. Finally, the behavioral component includes people's actions in relation to their work, which may include being tardy, staying late, or pretending to be ill in order to avoid work.

Need of the Study:

The main needs of the study are as follows

- Employee satisfaction and retention have always been important issues for employees.
- To analyse the level of satisfaction of employees towards various HR activities of the IT companies.
- To analyse the variables related to level of satisfaction which will be useful for the IT companies to know about the perception of employees in future period of time.

Review of Literature:

Salam (2017) examined to exploring the reasons for job satisfaction among the employees of an organisation. The selected variables in the study are Job satisfaction and turnover intention of the employees. The researcher found that the HR manager has to discover the problems faced by the employees and take initiatives to reduce and increase job satisfaction

Rahman and Ashraf (2017) examined the levels of job satisfaction of the employees. The authors selected the variables like salary, welfare facilities and bonus facilities to assess the levels of job satisfaction. The researcher found that the working with present colleagues, leadership style, leave rules, job security,

performance appraisal and evaluation process, working plan and teamwork were recorded higher level of job satisfaction increased gradually among the bank employees.

Yee Poh Li (2019) aimed to analyze the impact of organisational climate on employee performance in a Malaysian Consultancy firm. A questionnaire was developed based on previous literature and analysis was done to determine the normality, reliability and validity of the scale. The independent variables in organisational climate in this research include role clarity, communication, career and development, reward system, relationship, teamwork and support and direction, while the dependent factor is the employee performance. The research design adopted in this study was combination of explanatory and descriptive with the method of cross sectional survey by distributing survey questionnaires, consisting 48 questions with Likert Scale (Strongly Agree -1 and 7 for Strongly Disagree). The sample size of the study was 45 which were collected using Random Probability sampling method. SPSS 2.0 was used in analyzing the collected data by using descriptive means and regression. This study found that all the selected organisational climate dimensions in this research have a positive and significant impact on employee performance from the regression test in SPSS 2.0. The beta coefficients for all the dimensions of organisational climate in this study are positive and high indicating the strong impact on employee performance.

Objectives of the Study:

- To analyse the demographic variables of the employees working with the IT industries
- To know the existing level of employees satisfaction in IT industries based on employee performance
- To find out the problem faced by employees in IT industries
- To analyze the relationship between job satisfaction and the performance of employees.
- To evaluate the perception of employees towards employee weather and climate.

Scope of the Study:

- Employee satisfaction and retention have always been important issues for employees.
- Useful to know levels of absenteeism and staff turnover can affect your bottom line, as temps, recruitment and retraining take their toll.
- The main scope of the study is that it will help the IT industries to know about the employee perception towards job satisfaction and the performance of employees, problems faced by employees in the IT industries, and employees desirability towards working conditions and policies which will help them in future period of time.

Research Methodology:

Research Design: Descriptive in nature.

Sources of Data:

- Primary data collection: Survey method was used to collect the primary data from the respondents.
- Secondary data collection: Articles, journals and websites
- Sampling method: Stratified sampling method.
- Sample size: 150 and the respondents are those who are working with various departments of IT industries in Coimbatore city.
- Tools for data collection: Percentage analysis, Descriptive statistics, Kruskal-Wallis test, One way-Anova and Rank correlation

Limitations of the Study:

- The sample size is limited to 150.
- There may be bias in collecting the data from the respondents.
- The area of study is limited to Coimbatore.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Demographic Variables of the Employees

Demographic Variables	Particulars	Frequency	Percent
Age	Above 20 years	1	0.7
	21-29 years	13	8.7
	30-39 years	19	12.7
	40-49 years	96	64
	50 years and above	21	14
	Total	150	100
Gender	Male	28	18.7
	Female	122	81.3
	Total	150	100
Experience	Above 2 Years	73	48.7
	3-5 years	21	14
	6-10 years	2	1.3

	11-15 years	10	6.7
	16 years and Above	44	29.3
	Total	150	100
Income	Less than Rs.5000	41	27.3
	Rs.5001-Rs.10000	93	62
	Rs.10001-Rs.25000	11	7.3
	More than Rs.25000	5	3.3
	Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

Out of 150 respondents 0.7% are Above 20 years, 8.7% are between 21-29 years, 12.7% are between 30-39 years, 64.0% are between 40-49 years, 14.0% are between 50 years and above. 18.7% are male, 81.3% are female. 48.7% have Above 2 Years of experience, 14.0% have 3-5 years of experience, 1.3% have 6-10 years of experience, 6.7% have 11-15 years of experience, 29.3% have 16 years and Above experience. 27.3% are earning less than Rs.5000 per month, 62.0% are earning between Rs.5001-Rs.10000, 7.3% are earning between Rs.10001-Rs.25000, 3.3% are earning more than Rs.25000per month.

Performance and Job Satisfaction:

A total of 11 variables were taken for the purpose of factor redemption of Performance and job satisfaction.

Table 2: KMO and Bartlett's Test for Performance and Job Satisfaction

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.486
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	194.015
	df	55
	Sig.	.000

Source: Computed Data

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy is at 0.486 which is greater than 0.5. It depicts that the KMO value is adequate and the factors are normally distributed

Table 3: Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cum. %	Total	% of Variance	Cum. %	Total	% of Variance	Cum. %
1	2.224	20.218	20.218	2.224	20.218	20.218	1.851	16.826	16.826
2	1.408	12.802	33.020	1.408	12.802	33.020	1.477	13.431	30.257
3	1.234	11.221	44.241	1.234	11.221	44.241	1.337	12.152	42.409
4	1.113	10.115	54.356	1.113	10.115	54.356	1.234	11.219	53.628
5	1.043	9.482	63.837	1.043	9.482	63.837	1.123	10.209	63.837
6	.930	8.456	72.294						
7	.868	7.889	80.183						
8	.767	6.968	87.151						
9	.606	5.506	92.657						
10	.492	4.472	97.129						
11	.316	2.871	100.000						
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.									

Source: Computed Data

The components having Eigenvalue more than 1 are taken as components for the study. With the study the first component contributes 20.21%, the second component contributes 33.02%. the third component contributes 44.24%, the fourth component contributes 54.35%, the fifth component contributes 63.83%.

Table 4: Rotated Component Matrix

	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
Performance planning /goal setting	.025	.845	-.099	.043	.171
Performance evaluation	-.004	.116	.802	-.029	.040

Development planning	.103	.812	.255	-.025	-.109
360-degree feedback	.425	-.033	.612	.018	.028
Informal feedback	.829	-.137	-.013	.167	.161
Coaching and/or Mentoring	.686	.106	-.016	-.142	-.002
Training / Skill development	.276	.123	.146	.779	.166
Leadership development	-.252	-.128	.237	.057	-.583
Rewards / Incentives	.209	.090	.154	-.754	.226
Discipline	.539	.137	.275	.053	-.157
Overall PMS	-.162	-.037	.260	.002	.781
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. Rotation Method: Quartimax with Kaiser Normalization.					

The common variables above 0.5 are taken for decision making process of the study. The variables are Performance planning /goal setting (0.845), Performance evaluation (0.802), Development planning (0.812), Informal feedback (0.829).

Descriptive Statistics:

Table 5: Performance and Job Satisfaction

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
PJS1	150	2.71	1.166
PJS2	150	2.87	1.079
PJS3	150	3.37	.943
PJS4	150	2.69	.970

Source: Computed Data

The above table shows the descriptive statistics for the reduced factors using factor analysis of Performance and job satisfaction. It depicts that the respondents are Dissatisfied towards performance planning and goal setting by the IT companies(2.71), also on the performance evaluation (2.87), and also towards the feedbacks provided are Informal (2.69), and Satisfied towards planning of development(3.37).

Table 6: Organization Weather

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
OW1	150	4.29	.745
OW2	150	4.27	.926
OW3	150	4.16	.977
OW4	150	4.11	1.040

Source: Computed Data

The above table shows the descriptive statistics for the reduced factors using factor analysis of Organization weather. It depicts that the respondents are Strongly agree towards solving of problems through efficient solutions (4.29), also towards need of best for each individual is a primary concern in this organization (4.27), people concerning about the need of best for themselves(4.16), and also on the expectation of care towards individual while making decisions(4.11).

Table 7: Organization Climate

	N	Mean	SD
OC1	150	4.15	.888
OC2	150	4.41	.744
OC3	150	4.46	.672
OC4	150	4.27	.926
OC5	150	4.41	.779

Source: Computed Data

The above table shows the descriptive statistics for the reduced factors using factor analysis of Organization climate. It depicts that the respondents are Strongly agree towards feeling with bursting energy in the work(4.15), finding work they do is full of meaning and purpose(4.41), time flies when they are working (4.46), being enthusiastic about their job (4.27), ability to continue work for very long periods at a time (4.41).

Table 8: Comparison between Demographic Variables and Job Satisfaction and Organization Weather and Climate

Ho1: There is no relationship between gender and level of satisfaction towards job satisfaction and Organization weather and climate

	Gender	N	Mean Rank	Chi-Square	Asymp. Sig.
Relationship between job satisfaction and the performance of employees	Male	28	76.75	0.029	0.865
	Female	122	75.21		
	Total	150			
Organization weather	Male	28	66.38	1.665	0.197
	Female	122	77.59		
	Total	150			
Organization climate	Male	28	70.32	0.520	0.471
	Female	122	76.69		
	Total	150			
Organization performance and job satisfaction	Male	28	68.89	0.799	0.371
	Female	122	77.02		
	Total	150			

Source: Computed Data

There is no relationship between gender and Relationship between job satisfaction and the performance of employees (0.865), Organization weather (0.197), Organization climate (0.471), Organization performance and job satisfaction (0.371) and level of satisfaction towards job satisfaction and Organization weather and climate

Table 9: Comparison between Demo Graphic Variables and Job Satisfaction and Organization Weather and Climate

Ho2: There is no significant difference between occupation and level of satisfaction and job satisfaction and Organization weather and climate

		N	Mean	SD	F	Sig
Relationship between job satisfaction and the performance of employees	Developers	18	2.69	0.584	0.841	0.474
	Software testing	63	2.64	0.600		
	Backend support	40	2.82	0.643		
	Administrative Staff	29	2.64	0.478		
	Total	150	2.69	0.588		
Organization weather	Developers	18	4.21	0.963	1.755	0.158
	Software testing	63	4.10	0.876		
	Backend support	40	4.47	0.734		
	Administrative Staff	29	4.09	0.917		
	Total	150	4.21	0.866		
Organization climate	Developers	18	4.33	0.713	0.793	0.500
	Software testing	63	4.25	0.710		
	Backend support	40	4.47	0.689		
	Administrative Staff	29	4.37	0.678		
	Total	150	4.34	0.697		
Organization performance and job satisfaction	Developers	18	2.75	0.527	3.776	0.012
	Software testing	63	2.81	0.653		
	Backend support	40	2.91	0.485		
	Administrative Staff	29	3.22	0.564		
	Total	150	2.91	0.597		

Source: Computed Data

There is a significant difference between occupation and Relationship between job satisfaction and the performance of employees (0.474), Organization weather (0.158), Organization climate (0.500), and level of satisfaction towards job satisfaction and Organization weather and climate

There is no significant difference between occupation and Organization performance and job satisfaction (0.012) and level of satisfaction towards job satisfaction and Organization weather and climate.

Rank Correlation:

Table 10: Level of Importance towards Performance and Job Satisfaction

S.No	Particulars	X	Y	R1	R2	D	D ²
1	Training	50	16	2	3	-1	1
2	Health and safety	77	41	1	1	0	0
3	Insurance	39	34	3	2	1	1
4	Career development opportunity	16	15	4	4	0	0
							2
						1-R	0.23
						R	0.77

Source: Computed Data

The above table shows about the rank correlation for level of importance towards performance and job satisfaction. The correlation value for the compare factor is at 0.77 which is greater than 0.7. It shows that high correlation exists between the compared factors. Based on the ranks given a higher importance is been given to health and safety of the employees with the IT companies.

Table 11: Reason for Lack on Job Satisfaction

S.No	Reason for lack on job satisfaction	X	Y	R1	R2	D	D ²
1	Lack of control over your work	55	31	2	4	-2	4.00
2	Lack of recognition for work done	22	72	5	2	3	9.00
3	Job insecurity	85	57	1	3	-2	4.00
4	Fear of layoffs	36	74	4	1	3	9.00
5	Harassment	51	25	3	5	-2	4.00
							30.00
						1-R	0.25
						R	0.75

Source: Computed Data

The above table shows about the rank correlation for reason for lack on job satisfaction. The correlation value for the compare factor is at 0.75 which is greater than 0.7. It shows that high correlation exists between the compared factors. Based on the ranks given a higher importance is been given to Job insecurity as a reason for lack on job satisfaction.

Findings:

- Most of the respondents are between 40-49 years of age.
- Maximum of the respondents are female.
- Most of the respondents have above 2 years of experience.
- Majority of the respondents are earning between Rs.5001-Rs.10000 per month
- Maximum of the respondents are somewhat satisfied with bonus.
- Most of the respondents are dissatisfied towards superiors interest shown in employee welfare development and encouragement.
- Maximum of the respondents opinion about the group insurance scheme followed in the IT industries are good.

Suggestions:

- The IT industries can change their group insurance policy as the employees are dissatisfied towards the insurance policy provided by the IT industries.
- A convenient working culture has to be given by the IT industries as they feel the disturbances and inconvenience at the workplace.
- A Proper training can be provided by the IT industries to their managers to improve their managerial skill which leads to higher level of satisfaction among employees.
- In service training increases employee's knowledge of the job responsibilities, promotes high morale, aids to perform effectively and demonstrate the ability for future professional growth, the sum of which results in an increment in both quantity and quality of services. Hence, professionals of all cadres should also be encouraged to participate in continuing education program like short-term courses, workshops, and training program. The technology-oriented aspects must be given priority over traditional and outmoded subjects while conducting training programs.
- Creation of Job Satisfaction is not an easy job for the management. It requires efforts and arrangement. So, the Organization should conduct a job satisfaction survey of their employees at least once a year for continuous improvement and according that they should take necessary steps to improve because motivated employees work with pride deriving a sense of the satisfaction in their work to contribute to

the success of the organizations.

Conclusion:

The conclusion is that the employees have a higher level of dissatisfaction towards the performance of the IT industries towards various factors which should take as a serious note to rectify the issues so that the level of satisfaction can be improved which leads to increase in productivity with employees in near future.

References:

1. Spector, P. E. (1997). Job satisfaction: Application, assessment, causes, and consequences (Vol. 3). Sage publications.
2. Salam (2017) The Impact of Positive Attitudes on Job Satisfaction. Pakistan Business Review, 329-324.
3. Rahman and Ashraf (2017) Personal, the management of human resources. London: Prentice-Hall International, Inc. 89-103
4. Yee Poh Li (2019) "A Study on the impact of organisational climate on employee performance in a Malaysian consultancy" International Journal of Accounting & Business Management, Vol. 5 (No.1), PP 1-13.